

A prototype with Xenon to simulate the future advance refrigeration unit for cooling of silicon detector trackers

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ABSTRACT

The Large Hadron Collider (LHC) will soon undergo the Phase III Upgrade resulting in radiation levels extent never achieved before. Therefore, both detector cooling system and mechanical supports for the future particle trackers should be also upgraded as the current refrigeration technology applying CO₂ is not sufficient to avoid the thermal runaway of silicon sensors due to the CO₂ triple point temperature (≈ -56 deg C). Krypton has been selected as the most promising natural alternative to CO₂ for the ultra-low temperature operating at high-pressure levels ensuring a clean and efficient cooling inside the sensors and electronics. However, the thermophysical properties of Krypton required the design of a new cooling cycle different to that developed for CO₂. Therefore, as a first step of this large study, in order to prove the Krypton cooling cycle concept in laboratory conditions, a small-scale prototype using Xenon as working fluid was designed and is under construction in Varmeteknisk laboratory at NTNU (Trondheim, Norway). Xenon was selected as its critical temperature and pressure were suitable to emulate the working conditions typical for Krypton-based detector cooling system while at the same time offered the possibility to analyze the thermal performance and behavior of noble gases in easily attainable temperatures typical for commercial refrigeration (down to -30 deg C).

In this work, an ejector-supported cycle with a dedicated almost-fully passive evaporator loop Xenon was designed and numerically evaluated. The controllability and stability of the cycle, as well as the entering condition, setpoint and cooling rate in the evaporator were the main priorities of the study.

Keyword: Ejector, refrigeration, supercritical, transcritical, Xenon

1. INTRODUCTION

As broadly experienced, CO₂ has proven over the years to be the perfect candidate for cooling of the silicon detector trackers at CERN. Radiation hardness, low GWP and high thermal performance are the main criteria's among others (Verlaat et al. (2008)). The actual cooling system rely on a well-established concept namely 2PACL (two-phase accumulator pumped loop) that was inspired on satellite cooling application, where passive cooling was the main requirement (Verlaat et al. (2008); Verlaat (2007)). With the next generation of higher performance particle colliders, one on hand energy and collision rate will increase but the targeted operational temperature of the cooling system will decrease to sustain the integrity and reliability of the silicon sensors installed all over the detector, to prevent from the phenomena of the thermal runaway (Beck and Viehhauser (2010)).

For the future temperature (Group (2020)) range of interest ($\approx -70/-80^\circ\text{C}$) a new high-pressure working fluid will be required. A preliminary study based on thermo-hydraulic performance showed that the noble gas Krypton is the most promising coolant in detector application (Contiero et al. (2022)). Because of the required cooling starting at ambient conditions during the detector lifetime, a completely new cycle based on a hybrid ejector-vapor compression system was proposed (Contiero and Barroca (2022)). The new cooling concept should be proved experimentally and therefore a small-scale prototype was designed. To facilitate the working conditions, the noble gas Xenon is proposed because of its warmer critical temperature and pressure-similarity with Krypton. The design of the facility as well as numerical investigation of the cycle are here presented.

2. EJECTOR-SUPPORTED CYCLE WITH PASSIVE EVAPORATOR LOOP

The silicon detector consists in several layers of silicon sensor mounted on a substructure called staves and installed around the collision point. The distance covered by those staves are in general of several meters and all over cooling is needed to prevent an overheating of the sensors. Because of mass saving reasons, the cooling lines have also small diameters (Verlaat and Noite (2012)). Few times during the detector lifetime, cooling starts from ambient conditions. However, the cooling rate

of the sensors must be accurately controlled to avoid any thermal shock and possible damaging of the sensors. In accordance with this aspect and thermophysical properties of Krypton, a new cycle capable of moving from the warm to the cold area while connected to a detector was designed (Contiero and Barroca (2022)).

Figure 1: Simplified PI&D of the Krypton cooling unit.

The starting area is in supercritical state where pressure – temperature are independent of each other. However, in supercritical state the pressure in the high side is determined by the relationship between refrigerant charge, volume and temperature. By further charging the system, the system can be conditioned to operate at high pressures where the isothermal lines are nearly vertical and thus preventing a fast overcooling. When the compressor starts, the heat is first rejected to a CO₂ multi-evaporating cooling system before throttling part of the flow back to the compressor suction port. By operating in this triangle cycle, the cooling rate can be minimized. The remaining Krypton flow will undergo a further gas cooling process before entering the ejector which acts as a recirculating device. By further cooling the high-pressure side and by removing part of the refrigerant mass, if needed, the pressure will start falling bringing the ejector cycle towards the critical point (transcritical operation). In this sense, the cooling cycle moves gradually from the right hand side to the left hand side in the pressure-enthalpy diagram according to the detector temperature. An interesting feature of the novel cycle is that it can be tailored to operate with continuity delivering at the detector either supercritical cold conditions or in subcritical conditions in subcooled state to ensure that in this latter case boiling starts at the entrance of the evaporator (Petagna et al. (2018)). In the same manner way of the 2PACL, the evaporator loop should be almost fully-passive because of the harsh accessible areas around the detector. The demonstrator of the Krypton cooling cycle is the Xenon prototype described in detail in the following section, considering same start-up conditions (supercritical state) and operation at high-reduced pressure during subcritical conditions.

2.1. Design approach evaporator loop & Ejector

The design of a system working both in supercritical state and as a two-phase system is rather complex since every component will strongly affect the overall performance and the control strategy will differ according to the operating envelope. Therefore,

the design followed up a stepwise approach, summarized as follows:

- For measurement and accuracy purposes of the particle experiments the overall mass around the detector must be kept as low as possible and therefore it is crucial first to define the optimum size of the evaporator cooling lines based on thermo-hydraulic performance, considering two aspects: the vapor quality margin to overheat the detector (< 35%) to exploit the highest heat transfer coefficients, secondly to maintain acceptable pressure and related temperature gradients along the cooling pipe (3-5 K maximum)
- Being the ejector the recirculating device for the flow at the detector outlet and considering the easiness to provide a small pressure lift with the ejector rather than a large pressure lift, the remaining components of the evaporator loop were designed. Once the optimum size of the evaporator line is defined and accordingly pressure gradients are calculated, the available gradient ($\Delta p_{ejector} = \Delta p_{evaporator} + \Delta p_{capillary} + \Delta p_{concentricline}$) is shared between the concentric line and the capillary. The capillaries should introduce a predominant pressure drop at the evaporator entrance to ensure that, under the most unbalanced situation, the highest load in one of the cooling branches will still invoke enough liquid flow to avoid dry-out. This approach is known to be an effective method to balance an hydraulic circuits with many lines sharing the upstream and downstream pressures. The concentric line was designed such that the subcooled liquid can potentially reach the outlet return temperature while maintaining low pressure drops on both sides
- According to the hydraulic circuit designed and related Δp , the additional boundary conditions given by the refrigeration system correspond to multiple operational curves. Therefore the ejector geometry can be optimized to be able to supply the necessary pressure lift under all the operating conditions investigated
- As latest, the gas cooler section and the compressor can be sized to couple the necessary capacity and pressure levels required by ejector & evaporator loop

2.2. Designing the evaporator loop

For the design of the evaporator loop (Figure 1, blue line) it is crucial to predict the pressure drop and heat transfer behaviour. Along the cooling lines the flow condition and thermophysical properties change and therefore a finite difference method have been used. In the two-phase area the pressure drop and heat transfer rely on the general correlations provided by Friedel and Kandlikar (Friedel (1979), Kandlikar (1990)), respectively. For the single phase liquid and vapor, the correlation of Darcy-Weisbach for pressure drop and Gnielinski for heat transfer have been used. As described above, the evaluation of the evaporator performance is the first step. The numerical model was implemented in both Matlab and Dymola environments (self-defined correlation), where boundary conditions are set on both inlet-outlet of the cooling tube so requiring an iterative solving method to converge to a stable solution. Figure 2 indicates the progressive increase of flow as the evaporator outlet temperature increases. This trend can be justified by the operating reduced pressure: closer to the critical point the thermophysical properties are better but the latent heat of vaporization tends to zero. This means that a larger flow is needed to avoid the risk of dry-out and consequently the pressure drop will increase. The case at the highest evaporating temperature (10°C) has been considered as design case.

Figure 2: Mass flow and pressure drop (with Xenon) for a standard detector (length = 1 [m], $d_i = 2$ [mm], Heat load = 150 [W]) for reduced pressure in the range 0.57 - 0.88 (a). Example of temperature - pressure profile prediction along the cooling line (b).

Before describing the dimensions of the concentric line used to bring the fluid in subcooled state at the entrance of the capillary section, it is important to point out the constraints of working at high-reduced pressures where the future Krypton cooling system is required to operate (-70 to -80 °C, corresponding to reduced pressures in the range $\approx 0.84 - 0.62$). The same should occur for the Xenon prototype here designed. On one hand to encourage an uniform flow distribution along parallel cooling lines (in our case three evaporators are chosen) does require the introduction of a predominant pressure gradient upstream to the detector, along the capillary section. On the other hand, for stability reasons, the receiver should operate in the two-phase area where its pressure level can be actively controlled with the CGBV (bypass downstream the first gas cooler) rather than with charging-discharging of the refrigerant mass as would happen upstream in supercritical state. Indeed, the available gradient (ejector pressure lift) requires to keep as low as possible the gradients in the concentric line in order to gain extra Δp on the capillary side. By doing so, an additional advantage is a more precise control of the detector operating temperature: indeed, if the pressure drops on the return two-phase flow are rather small, controlling the ejector suction nozzle pressure means to control the evaporating temperature in the detector, except for the small offset given by the Δp on the return line. The concentric line has been designed following the same approach in use today: the liquid line is placed on the inner side to shield it from ambient heating and so requiring the insulation only on the outer line (return from detector outlet). Figure 3 shows the temperature and pressure profiles for the warm and cold streams, while Table 1 illustrates the geometrical parameter. Non-linear profile on the liquid side is expected since the specific heat capacity varies a lot close to the critical point. The long length required is the result of different factors: the extreme low temperature difference among the two streams, the requirement of maintaining as low as possible the pressure drops on the return two-phase flow by adopting bigger diameters, the extreme low thermal conductivity of Xenon which negatively impacts the two-phase heat transfer coefficient.

Figure 3: Temperature profiles liquid & two-phase return flow (a). Representation in the Xenon p-h diagram (b).

Table 1: Geometry and pressure drop results for the concentric line.

Concentric line	d_i mm	d_o mm	Thickness mm	Length m	Δp bar
Liquid line	6	8	1	12	0.2
Two-phase line	12	16	2	12	0.1698

Although flow and inlet conditions have been evaluated from the evaporator section to maintain flow boiling in the range 0-35%, a partial bypass of the liquid flow through the concentric line must be implemented. Indeed, working at high reduced pressures means that the fluid is compressible and so a cooling down due to expansion is present downstream the capillary section. To overcome this cooling a minimum heat is required to tune the inlet conditions at the entrance of the capillary to prevent from poor heat transfers (subcooled liquid) at the entrance of the detector. The capillary dedicated to each evaporator has been sized as 1/16" tube with approximately 12 cm length.

As last, the entire evaporator loop was simulated in Dymola environment to analyze temperature-pressure profiles along

the loop. Figure 4 shows the different profiles for two operating conditions, maintaining constant the pressure lift over the loop (≈ 3.5 bar). This choice is based on a specific ejector control strategy to operate with almost constant pressure lift under flow boiling conditions. Therefore, an iterative calculation is performed to converge to a stable value of mass flow rate. This exercise does not only help to evaluate different ejector suction conditions according to the heat load imposed on the evaporators & operating temperature, but it also proves the effectiveness of the larger pressure drop gradient along the capillary (ratio $\Delta p_{capillary}/\Delta p_{evaporator} \approx 4$). As it can be seen on Figure 4 (a) the saturated liquid is first subcooled.

Figure 4: Temperature, pressure and quality profiles along the evaporator loop using Xenon (Detector setpoint = 10 [°C], full load 450 [W]) (a,b). Temperature, pressure and quality profiles along the evaporator loop (Detector setpoint = 0 [°C], full load 450 [W]) (c,d).

The temperature later increases before entering the capillary section due to the mixing with the liquid bypassed, entering the evaporator section at saturated conditions or slightly in the two-phase area (Figure 4 (b)). The pressure drops along the capillary, as well as the temperature due to compressibility of the fluid at high working pressure. In the evaporator section the quality increases linearly because of the constant heat flux imposed, while pressure drops cause temperature drops. The outlet two-phase flow is then further vaporized in the return line. The second case with a decreased evaporating temperature indicates the effect of a constant pressure lift strategy: larger flow is invoked in the loop, resulting in an overflow trough the evaporator (Figure 4 (d)). This overflow is reflected in a larger liquid content that must be driven back to the liquid receiver by the ejector, thus requiring a floating control of the high-pressure side.

Figure 5 shows the method implemented to obtain a better flow distribution: the flow resistance in liquid state (capillary) does not depend on the absorbed heat load as happens downstream in the evaporator section. The worst-case scenario would occur when some of the cooling lines are unpowered: in this case a larger overflow is invoked in the off-powered line to obtain the same pressure drop of the loaded line. Larger is the pressure drop introduced, less overflow is needed in the off-power line. The unpowered branch will experience a slightly larger overflow, decreasing inlet temperature-pressure at the

entrance of the evaporator section. Consequently, the common vapor content at the suction line of the ejector will decrease as a function of how many evaporators are unpowered.

Figure 5: Temperature, pressure and quality profiles along the evaporator loop with Xenon (Detector setpoint = 10 [°C], part-load 300 [W]) (a,b).

2.3 Ejector simulation

The prediction of the pressure losses along the evaporator loop is fundamental to obtain a correct design of the ejector. It works both as a recirculation device and a medium to accurately controlled the setpoint in the evaporator. The controllability of the evaporator outlet conditions is ensured by proper adjustment of the motive conditions, mainly in terms of pressure-temperature, as function of the suction conditions (evaporator outlet). The 1D model developed by Banasiak and Hafner (2011) was used to demonstrate the suitability of a small CO₂ LP (low-pressure lift) Danfoss ejector (model LP1925, cartridge CTM ELP 60)). The inputs used in the simulation model were motive and suction conditions, as well as the ejector geometry. Figure 6 illustrates the pressure lift invoked by the ejector under different values of entrainment ratio, while keeping constant motive conditions in two different cases.

Figure 6: Available pressure lift provided by the ejector and its efficiency for different motive conditions and different setpoints in the detector (using Xenon).

The motive inlet temperature was chosen equal to 25°C, normally considered as ambient temperature. It can be seen how strongly the motive pressure influence the potential of lifting the suction flow for a given value of entrainment ratio. The

simulation shows how, accordingly to the estimation of the hydraulic losses along the evaporator loop, at 95 bar there is excessive potential that should be reduced otherwise the controllability of the detector outlet would be lost. In case of an extra pressure lift delivered by the ejector, the valve (Figure 1) installed right before the suction nozzle serves as balancing device to couple the extra work potential available and the hydraulic losses in the evaporator loop. The second case (Figure 6(b)) indeed prove that a floating control of the motive pressure is required. However, it is always recommended to have extra lift available in case of excessive pressure losses along the loop.

3. THE XENON PROTOTYPE

The cooling concept of the future Krypton cooling unit will be tested experimentally and for this purpose a Xenon setup was designed (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Detailed P&ID of the Xenon prototype under construction with temperature-pressure sensors.

The remaining elements of the cycle such as compressor, gas coolers, internal heat exchanger and the liquid receiver are CO2 high-pressure rated components. The heat rejection occurs via a two water gas coolers. Because of the lack of an oil-free compressor rated for such pressure levels and fluid, a standard piston compressor will be used. The oil lubrication introduces several disadvantages: considering the extreme dynamic system, an inversion temperature phenomenon would invoke a drastic density change especially on the low-pressure side while the cycle undergoes the supercritical and transcritical operation. As side effect, the oil recovery from the liquid receiver will become extremely challenging as the oil will float on the top. The yellow line and the buffer tank are specifically introduced to overcome this issue. The recovery of the oil from the low-pressure side is performed after every operation period of the unit: the correct setting of the metering and three-way valve would allow to discharge part of the liquid Xenon into the buffer tank so that after being heated by ambient temperature, the pressure-density is such to collect the oil at the bottom of the receiver. Afterwards, the liquid Xenon previously stored will turn into supercritical fluid before being restored into the main loop by the compressor. The buffer tank can also act as a charging-discharging device of the refrigerant charge. The oil recovery represents an issue exclusively in the experimental demonstrator of the Krypton cycle, while in the real system connected to the detector the refrigeration unit is oil-free.

Because the Xenon demonstrator replicates the Krypton cooling concept, same conditions at the startup must also occur. At room temperature Xenon can be either in supercritical or in two-phase state, considering a critical temperature approximately around 17 °C. However, the supercritical cooldown process that the detector experiences starts far from the critical point in the case of Krypton. This induces to pre-condition the starting point of the Xenon test-rig. Indeed, once the system is charged to the required pressure level, it can be heated up by placing it inside a climatic chamber where hot air can be blown in. By providing heat, the starting point will move through the isochoric line (as function of the charge) until approximately a temperature ≈ 50 °C. Now the cooldown process can start to gently bring the detector to the required setpoint.

3.1 Full-cycle modelling

The cycle supplied with the geometrical data was modelled in the Dymola environment to study the thermal equilibriums of the different operational states in transcritical mode. Pressure drops on the gas cooler section were neglected and a constant overall heat transfer coefficient was used in that specific section. The ejector was modelled for sake of simplicity as a variable controlled geometry (throat of the motive nozzle) with a constant efficiency of 25% defined as in Elbel and Hrnjak (2008) . In practice this would correspond to a single geometry with modulated cross section area of the motive nozzle (continuous control with a regulating needle) or a battery of several parallel ejector (stepwise control). The full-cycle simulation is particularly useful to understand the state parameters between the different sections of the cycle. Figure 8 shows the transcritical operation at the design case (detector outlet 10°C) under different heating powers. The operation

Figure 8: Transcritical operation of the ejector-supported cycle considering full and part-load conditions. In green transcritical cycle with colder motive inlet temperature and fixed motive nozzle area.

of the cycle is in a way independent from the compressor: whatever is the flow elaborated by the compressor (volumetric efficiency assumed equal to 60%), the CGBV (cold-gas bypass valve) will maintain the receiver pressure under control. This implies that a frequency driven compressor could be useful only to avoid excessive discharge temperature. The triangle cycle helps to minimize the sudden change of the compressor suction conditions as stability and reliability are favoured over

efficiency. As consequence, the flow rate through the motive nozzle is given. This means that the motive cross-sectional area should be actively controlled to maintain the detector setpoint. As it can be seen, whenever the heat load imposed by the detector decreases for a given temperature setpoint, much more liquid should return to the receiver.

Different suction conditions would require a modulating control of the discharge pressure to ensure to not have any surplus-deficit of expansion work available. Indeed, with fixed geometry ejector one degree of freedom is lost: the detector outlet setpoint cannot be actively controlled as the high-pressure will be a result of the flow bypassed and the constant flow area. Moreover, any change of the inlet motive temperature would also invoke a different flow through the detector that could not be adjusted because the high-pressure cannot be regulated (green cycle). In this case, much less flow is invoked by the ejector potentially leading to a risk of thermal runaway of the sensors as well as dry-out at the evaporator outlet.

The transcritical cycle was also analyzed for different setpoint in the detector (Figure 9). Considering the motive temperature constant, the high-pressure varies to follow the evaporating temperature. In practice, a further closing of the CGBV would cause a drop of the receiver pressure. Parallel regulation of the CGBV-ejector flow area is required to lower the setpoint while maintaining safe conditions in the detector.

Figure 9: Transcritical operation of the ejector-supported cycle with a lower setpoints in the detector, with floating control of the receiver and discharge pressure according to control ejector strategy of constant pressure lift.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this work a small-scale Xenon unit was designed to prove the cooling concept of the Krypton cooling unit. The evaporator loop which replicates the detector layout has been carefully designed, focusing on the different requirements such as pressure losses, boiling starting at the entrance of the detector and hydraulic balance of the multiple cooling lines. According to thermo-hydraulic performance of the passive evaporator loop, numerical simulations of the ejector have showed that a floating control of the discharge pressure is required to follow different operational points in the detector. The novel hybrid

ejector cycle is currently under construction based on the results presented above. The numerical modelling of the real-sized cycle helps a lot to estimate thermal equilibrium, as well as refrigerant charge and the different filling levels (liquid) in the receiver which should never be empty of liquid or overfilled. The simulation has identified the possible future control strategy of the cycle: being the evaporator loop almost-fully passive, the desired temperature-pressure profile can be induced indirectly by a parallel control of the CGBV-ejector motive nozzle area. Indeed, as for the 2PACL where the two-phase accumulator is the detector regulator, here the CGBV can be seen as a receiver controller with which the ejector must be modulated to ensure proper operation during design and off-design conditions.

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REFERENCES

- K. Banasiak and A. Hafner. 1D computational model of a two-phase R744 ejector for expansion work recovery. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 50(11):2235–2247, 2011. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijthermalsci.2011.06.007>.
- G. Beck and G. Viehhauser. Analytic model of thermal runaway in silicon detectors. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 618(1-3):131–138, 2010.
- L. Contiero and P. Barroca. Hybrid cycle with Krypton for cooling of future silicon detectors in HEP. *Forum on Tracking Detector Mechanics*, 2022.
- L. Contiero, P. Barroca, A. Hafner, B. Verlaat, P. Petagna, and K. Banasiak. Krypton, applied as refrigerant for cooling of silicon detector trackers. *International Institute of Refrigeration*, GL2022:14, 2022. doi: [10.18462/iir.gl2022.0203.0031](https://doi.org/10.18462/iir.gl2022.0203.0031).
- S. Elbel and P. Hrnjak. Ejector refrigeration: an overview of historical and present developments with an emphasis on air-conditioning applications. *International Refrigeration and Air conditioning conference*, 2008.
- L. Friedel. Improved friction pressure drop correlations for horizontal and vertical two-phase pipe flow. *European Two-Phase Flow Group Meeting, Ispra, Italy*, 18:485–491, 1979.
- E. D. R. P. Group. The 2021 ECFA detector research and development roadmap. *Report: CERN-ESU-017*, 2020. doi: [10.17181/CERN.XDPL.W2EX](https://doi.org/10.17181/CERN.XDPL.W2EX).
- S. G. Kandlikar. A general correlation for saturated two-phase flow boiling heat transfer inside horizontal and vertical tubes. *Journal of Heat and Mass transfer*, 112:219–228, 1990.
- P. Petagna, B. Verlaat, and A. Francescon. Two-phase thermal management of silicon detectors for high energy physics. In *Encyclopedia of Two-Phase Heat Transfer and Flow III: Macro and Micro Flow Boiling and Numerical Modeling Fundamentals Volume 4: Special Boiling Topics*, volume 4, pages 335–412. World Scientific, 2018.
- B. Verlaat. Controlling a 2-phase CO₂ loop using a 2-phase accumulator. *International Conference of Refrigeration*, 2007.
- B. Verlaat and J. Noite. Design considerations of long length evaporative CO₂ cooling lines. *Proceedings of 10th IIF/IIR Gustav Lorentzen Conference on Natural Refrigerants*, 2012.
- B. Verlaat, M. Van Beuzekom, and A. Van Lysebetten. CO₂ cooling for HEP experiments. *Topical Workshop on Electronics for Particle Physics*, 2008. doi: [10.5170/CERN-2008-008.328](https://doi.org/10.5170/CERN-2008-008.328).